

MODERN ASPECTS OF METAPHOR

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ANNOTATION.

People tend to use more emphatic and figurative speech, whereas others consider that this kind of speech is usually used by orators, speakers, writers and poets. However, people use metaphors in their day to day life without even knowing it.

Key words: Metaphor, speech, linguistics, philosophers.

INTRODUCTION

A metaphor, according to I.A.Richards, is “a shift”, a carrying over of a word from its normal use to a new use”. Metaphor has been studied by several linguists, philosophers and thinkers so far, and all of them more or less contributed to development of its theoretical value. Shakespeare, Goethe and Moliere helped to shape their languages, giving the members of their own linguistic communities new vibrant visions of the world; and if writers’ words and turns of phrases, rhythms, rhymes and metaphors continue to stimulate the way we express ourselves in everyday speech today, it is because the vitality of those authors’ worldviews has not died within our language.[1:58] To a greater or lesser extent, their ways of viewing the world continue to contribute to the ways we view the world. As the great German linguist Wilhelm von Humboldt put it, poets and philosophers strike their roots into reality, and in doing so, they cultivate and shape our vision of the world. Poets have the capacity to shape our interior world, the intimate space within us, just as much as ideologies structure the frameworks within which we live and work.

We would probably also say that the word is used metaphorically in order to achieve some artistic and rhetorical effect, since we speak and write. Indeed, this is a widely shared view—the most common conception of metaphor, both in scholarly circles and in the popular mind (which is not to say that this is the only view of metaphor). This traditional concept can be briefly characterized by pointing out five of its most commonly accepted features.[2:65] First, metaphor is a property of words; it is a linguistic phenomenon. The metaphorical use of lion is a characteristic of a linguistic expression (that of the word lion). Second, metaphor is used for some artistic and rhetorical purpose, such as when Shakespeare writes "all the world's a stage." Third, metaphor is based on a

resemblance between the two entities that are compared and identified. Achilles must share some features with lions in order for us to be able to use the word lion as a metaphor for Achilles. Fourth, metaphor is a conscious and deliberate use of words, and you must have a special talent to be able to do it and do it well. Only great poets or eloquent speakers, such as, say, Shakespeare and Churchill can be its masters. For instance, Aristotle makes the following statement to this effect: "The greatest thing by far is to have command of metaphor. This alone cannot be imparted by another; it is the mark of genius." Fifth, it is also commonly held that metaphor is a figure of speech that we can do without; we use it for special effects, and it is not an inevitable part of everyday human communication, let alone everyday human thought and reasoning. [3:77]

If we sum up the statement of Kovecses, metaphor is a phenomenon of language; it is used for special purposes, i.e. to give special "effect" to our speech; when metaphor is used, we name one thing with another not all people can handle to use metaphors, as it can demand effort; and finally without it we can also somehow manage our speech and daily life.

As one can see that these viewpoints changed everything, the contention's each band can oppose to the former traditional view and make more sense. Metaphor is indeed the result of mind rather than words. If we want to say something how actually we do this?! We first think (actually our brain does it) and deliver our thought by tongue, that is to by our speech. More often we use metaphor (or any other stylistic device) not only for artistic or aesthetic purpose, but also for stressing our point or sometimes we merely use it without any purpose. It is not only used by speakers, orators and writers, even most ordinary people use it. (Everyone says what a happy, sunny girl she was. It is an evitable part of our life, as human being tends to use fewer words and explain themselves from all the beginning. [4:95]

Conclusion

Metaphor has been thoroughly investigated by Uzbek linguists too. Some scholars dedicated their research on general meaning transfer ("ko'chim"), while others selected one specific type of meaning transfer such as metaphor (sometimes called as "istiora"). If we look up Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language there is given such a definition to metaphor: "the usage of a word or a phrase on the basis of similarity or comparison or used word or phrase in this meaning, istiora, majoz3, for instance tuning peg of dutar (musical

instrument) is called as “ear” in a metaphoric meaning.”As one can observe metaphoric word or phrase in one language cannot commensurate with the same meaning transfer in another one.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Milliy Ensiklopediasi. Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti. Tashkent.2000
2. Maslova V. A. Teoriya konceptual'noi metafory i ee rol' v sovremennyh lingvisticheskikh issle- dovaniyah. Lingvistika. Lingvokul'turologiya / V. A. Maslova // Sbornik nauchnyh trudov. Dnepro- petrovsk: Dnepropetrovskii nacional'nyi universitet, 2012.
3. Oparina E. O. Konceptual'naya metafora // Metafora v yazyke i tekste / Otv. red. V. N. Teliya. M., 1988.
4. Lakoff George & Johnson, Mark. Metaphors we live by. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1980.

